

RELATIONS AMONG FOURIER COEFFICIENTS OF CERTAIN ETA PRODUCTS

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Abstract

Certain arithmetic relations for the coefficients in the expansions of $(q)_\infty^r$, $(q)_\infty^r (q^t)_\infty^s$, $t = 2, 3, 4$, were studied by M. Newman, S. Cooper, M. D. Hirschhorn, R. Lewis, S. Ahlgren and R. Chapman. In this work, we prove similar identities for certain multi-product expansions using an elementary method.

1. Introduction

For an integer r , let

$$(q)_\infty^r = \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^n)^r = \sum_{n \geq 0} a_r(n) q^n, \quad (1.1)$$

where $q = e^{2\pi iz}$ and $\text{Im}(z) > 0$ and let

$$f_j(q) = (q)_\infty^{r_j} (q^2)_\infty^{s_j} (q^4)_\infty^{t_j}, \quad (1.2)$$

where r_j, s_j, t_j are certain specific integers (see theorem). In this article we consider the following products

$$f_i(q^l) f_k(q^m) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a(n) q^n \quad (l, m > 0),$$

and prove certain identities involving the Fourier coefficients $a(n)$ by elementary arguments. Similar identities for eta powers and products of two eta functions were earlier obtained by several authors [1, 3, 4, 5].

2. Statement of theorem

Let q be a complex number satisfying $|q| < 1$. It is readily checked that $(-q)_\infty = \frac{(q^2)_\infty^3}{(q)_\infty(q^4)_\infty}$.

Let

$$\begin{aligned} f_1(q) &= (q)_\infty, & f_7(q) &= f_1(-q) = \frac{(q^2)_\infty^3}{(q)_\infty(q^4)_\infty}, \\ f_2(q) &= (q)_\infty^3, & f_8(q) &= f_2(-q) = \frac{(q^2)_\infty^9}{(q)_\infty^3(q^4)_\infty^3}, \\ f_3(q) &= \frac{(q)_\infty^2}{(q^2)_\infty}, & f_9(q) &= f_3(-q) = \frac{(q^2)_\infty^5}{(q)_\infty^2(q^4)_\infty^2}, \\ f_4(q) &= \frac{(q^2)_\infty^2}{(q)_\infty}, & f_{10}(q) &= f_4(-q) = \frac{(q)_\infty(q^4)_\infty}{(q^2)_\infty}, \\ f_5(q) &= \frac{(q)_\infty^5}{(q^2)_\infty^2}, & f_{11}(q) &= f_5(-q) = \frac{(q^2)_\infty^{13}}{(q)_\infty^5(q^4)_\infty^5}, \\ f_6(q) &= \frac{(q^2)_\infty^5}{(q)_\infty^2}, & f_{12}(q) &= f_6(-q) = \frac{(q)_\infty^2(q^4)_\infty^2}{(q^2)_\infty}. \end{aligned}$$

Observe that each function $f_i(q)$ has the form $f_i(q) = (q)_\infty^{r_i}(q^2)_\infty^{s_i}(q^4)_\infty^{t_i}$, for certain integers r_i, s_i, t_i . By the triple product and quintuple product identities, we have [2, pp. 64–65 and 306–307], [4]

$$\begin{aligned} f_1(q) &= \sum_{\alpha \equiv 1 \pmod{6}} (-1)^{(\alpha-1)/6} q^{(\alpha^2-1)/24}, \\ f_2(q) &= \sum_{\alpha \equiv 1 \pmod{4}} \alpha q^{(\alpha^2-1)/8}, \\ f_3(q) &= \sum_{\alpha} (-1)^\alpha q^{\alpha^2}, \\ f_4(q) &= \sum_{\alpha \equiv 1 \pmod{4}} q^{(\alpha^2-1)/8}, \\ f_5(q) &= \sum_{\alpha \equiv 1 \pmod{6}} \alpha q^{(\alpha^2-1)/24}, \\ f_6(q) &= \sum_{\alpha \equiv 1 \pmod{3}} (-1)^{\alpha-1} \alpha q^{(\alpha^2-1)/3}, \end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

where in each case the sum is over all integers α , positive and negative, satisfying the given congruence.

For $1 \leq i \leq 12$, let $d_i = r_i + 2s_i + 4t_i$ and $\lambda_i = \left\lceil \frac{1}{2}(r_i + s_i + t_i) \right\rceil - 1$. Let

$$\begin{aligned} (e_1, e_2, \dots, e_{12}) &= (1, 3, 24, 3, 1, 8, 1, 3, 24, 3, 1, 8), \\ (n_1, n_2, \dots, n_{12}) &= (6, 4, 1, 4, 6, 3, 6, 4, 1, 4, 6, 3). \end{aligned}$$

Observe that $d_i = e_i$ unless $i = 3$ or 9 , in which case $d_3 = d_9 = 0$. For $1 \leq i \leq 12$ and p an odd prime, define $\epsilon_i(p) = \binom{a_i}{p}$, where $(a_1, \dots, a_{12}) = (3, -1, 1, 1, -3, -3, 6, -2, 1, 2, -6, -3)$. The main purpose of this article is to prove the following result.

Theorem. *Let ℓ and m be positive integers, and let $1 \leq j, k \leq 12$. Let $p > 3$ be any prime satisfying $\binom{-e_j e_k \ell m}{p} = -1$ and put $\Delta = \frac{p^2 - 1}{24}$. Let $f_j(q^\ell) f_k(q^m) = \sum_{n=0}^\infty a(n) q^n$. Then the coefficients $a(n)$ satisfy*

$$a(pn + (\ell d_j + m d_k) \Delta) = \epsilon_j(p) \epsilon_k(p) p^{\lambda_j + \lambda_k} a\left(\frac{n}{p}\right).$$

Example. ($j = 5, k = 10$) We have $f_5(q) = (q)_\infty^5 (q^2)_\infty^{-2}$ and $f_{10}(q) = (q)_\infty (q^2)_\infty^{-1} (q^4)_\infty$, so $(r_5, s_5, t_5) = (5, -2, 0)$, $(r_{10}, s_{10}, t_{10}) = (1, -1, 1)$, $d_5 = r_5 + 2s_5 + 4t_5 = 1$, $d_{10} = r_{10} + 2s_{10} + 4t_{10} = 3$, $\lambda_5 = \left\lceil \frac{1}{2}(r_5 + s_5 + t_5) \right\rceil - 1 = 1$, $\lambda_{10} = \left\lceil \frac{1}{2}(r_{10} + s_{10} + t_{10}) \right\rceil - 1 = 0$. $e_5 = 1$, $e_{10} = 3$, $\epsilon_5(p) = \binom{-3}{p}$, and $\epsilon_{10}(p) = \binom{2}{p}$. Let p be any prime satisfying $\binom{-e_5 e_{10} \ell m}{p} = -1$, i.e., $\binom{-3\ell m}{p} = -1$. Let $f_5(q^\ell) f_{10}(q^m) = \sum_{n=0}^\infty a(n) q^n$. Then the Theorem implies

$$a(pn + (\ell + 3m) \Delta) = \binom{-3}{p} \binom{2}{p} p a\left(\frac{n}{p}\right),$$

i.e.,

$$a(pn + (\ell + 3m) \Delta) = \binom{-6}{p} p a\left(\frac{n}{p}\right).$$

3. Proofs

We shall require the following elementary lemma, which we state without further comment.

Lemma. *Let ℓ and m be positive integers and let p be an odd prime satisfying $\binom{-\ell m}{p} = -1$. Let α and β be integers satisfying $\ell \alpha^2 + m \beta^2 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. Then $\alpha \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ and $\beta \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$.*

In order to illustrate the technique, we first prove the example, before proving the general statement of the theorem.

Proof of example. We have

$$f_5(q^\ell)f_{10}(q^m) = \sum_{\alpha \equiv 1 \pmod{6}} \alpha q^{\ell(\alpha^2-1)/24} \sum_{\beta \equiv 1 \pmod{4}} (-q^m)^{(\beta^2-1)/8},$$

so

$$\begin{aligned} a(n) &= \sum_{\substack{\alpha \equiv 1 \pmod{6}, \beta \equiv 1 \pmod{4} \\ \ell(\alpha^2-1)/24+m(\beta^2-1)/8=n}} \alpha(-1)^{(\beta^2-1)/8} \\ &= \sum_{\substack{\alpha \equiv 1 \pmod{6}, \beta \equiv 1 \pmod{4} \\ \ell\alpha^2+3m\beta^2=24n+\ell+3m}} \alpha(-1)^{(\beta^2-1)/8}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$a(pn + (\ell + 3m)\Delta) = \sum_{\substack{\alpha \equiv 1 \pmod{6}, \beta \equiv 1 \pmod{4} \\ \ell\alpha^2+3m\beta^2=24pn+(\ell+3m)p^2}} \alpha(-1)^{(\beta^2-1)/8}. \tag{3.1}$$

Now $\ell\alpha^2 + 3m\beta^2 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$, and the lemma implies $p \mid \alpha, p \mid \beta$. Let

$$\alpha = \left(\frac{-3}{p}\right)p\alpha', \quad \beta = \left(\frac{-1}{p}\right)p\beta'. \tag{3.2}$$

Then $\alpha' \equiv 1 \pmod{6}$ and $\beta' \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$. Also, modulo 2,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\beta^2 - 1}{8} - \frac{\beta'^2 - 1}{8} &= \frac{\beta^2 - \beta'^2}{8} \\ &= \frac{(p^2 - 1)\beta'^2}{8} \\ &\equiv \frac{p^2 - 1}{8} \\ &\equiv \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } p \equiv 1 \text{ or } 7 \pmod{8} \\ 1 & \text{if } p \equiv 3 \text{ or } 5 \pmod{8} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$(-1)^{(\beta^2-1)/8} = \left(\frac{2}{p}\right)(-1)^{(\beta'^2-1)/8}. \tag{3.3}$$

Substituting (3.2) and (3.3) into (3.1) we get

$$\begin{aligned} a(pn + (\ell + 3m)\Delta) &= \sum_{\substack{\alpha' \equiv 1 \pmod{6}, \beta' \equiv 1 \pmod{4} \\ \ell\alpha'^2+3m\beta'^2=24n/p+\ell+3m}} \left(\frac{-3}{p}\right)p\alpha' \left(\frac{2}{p}\right)(-1)^{(\beta'^2-1)/8} \\ &= \left(\frac{-6}{p}\right)p a\left(\frac{n}{p}\right). \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of the example. □

Proof of Theorem. Writing

$$f_j(q^\ell)f_k(q^m) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a(n)q^n,$$

we have, using (2.1),

$$a(n) = \sum_{\substack{\alpha \equiv 1 \pmod{n_j}, \beta \equiv 1 \pmod{n_k} \\ e_j \ell \alpha^2 + e_k m \beta^2 = 24n + d_j \ell + d_k m}} \phi_j(\alpha) \phi_k(\beta),$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_1(\alpha) &= (-1)^{(\alpha-1)/6}, & \phi_7(\alpha) &= (-1)^{(\alpha-1)/6 + (\alpha^2-1)/24}, \\ \phi_2(\alpha) &= \alpha, & \phi_8(\alpha) &= \alpha(-1)^{(\alpha^2-1)/8}, \\ \phi_3(\alpha) &= (-1)^\alpha, & \phi_9(\alpha) &= 1, \\ \phi_4(\alpha) &= 1, & \phi_{10}(\alpha) &= (-1)^{(\alpha^2-1)/8}, \\ \phi_5(\alpha) &= \alpha, & \phi_{11}(\alpha) &= \alpha(-1)^{(\alpha^2-1)/24}, \\ \phi_6(\alpha) &= (-1)^{\alpha-1} \alpha, & \phi_{12}(\alpha) &= (-1)^{\alpha-1 + (\alpha^2-1)/3} \alpha. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$a(pn + (\ell d_j + m d_k) \Delta) = \sum_{\substack{\alpha \equiv 1 \pmod{n_j}, \beta \equiv 1 \pmod{n_k} \\ e_j \ell \alpha^2 + e_k m \beta^2 = 24pn + p^2(d_j \ell + d_k m)}} \phi_j(\alpha) \phi_k(\beta).$$

Observe that $e_j \ell \alpha^2 + e_k m \beta^2 \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. The Lemma implies $p \mid \alpha$, $p \mid \beta$. Let

$$\alpha = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{-3}{p}\right) p \alpha' & \text{if } j = 1, 5, 6, 7, 11 \text{ or } 12 \\ \left(\frac{-1}{p}\right) p \alpha' & \text{if } j = 2, 4, 8 \text{ or } 10 \\ p \alpha' & \text{if } j = 3 \text{ or } 9, \end{cases}$$

$$\beta = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{-3}{p}\right) p \beta' & \text{if } k = 1, 5, 6, 7, 11 \text{ or } 12 \\ \left(\frac{-1}{p}\right) p \beta' & \text{if } k = 2, 4, 8 \text{ or } 10 \\ p \beta' & \text{if } k = 3 \text{ or } 9. \end{cases}$$

Then it is easily verified that $\alpha' \equiv 1 \pmod{n_j}$ and $\beta' \equiv 1 \pmod{n_k}$, and that $\phi_j(\alpha) = \epsilon_j(p) p^{\lambda_j} \phi_j(\alpha')$ and $\phi_k(\beta) = \epsilon_k(p) p^{\lambda_k} \phi_k(\beta')$. Consequently,

$$\begin{aligned} a(pn + (\ell d_j + m d_k) \Delta) &= \sum_{\substack{\alpha' \equiv 1 \pmod{n_j}, \beta' \equiv 1 \pmod{n_k} \\ e_j \ell \alpha'^2 + e_k m \beta'^2 = 24n/p + d_j \ell + d_k m}} \epsilon_j(p) \epsilon_k(p) p^{\lambda_j + \lambda_k} \phi_j(\alpha') \phi_k(\beta') \\ &= \epsilon_j(p) \epsilon_k(p) p^{\lambda_j + \lambda_k} a\left(\frac{n}{p}\right). \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of the theorem. □

Remark. Though our theorem can be proved using the theory of lacunary modular forms, we prefer to present an elementary proof for its simplicity.

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